

THE PATH TO SUPPLY CHAIN EXCELLENCE: A COMPREHENSIVE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR COMPETITIVENESS

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to emphasize the significance of competitiveness within the supply chain and propose a conceptual framework for Supply Chain Competitiveness (SCC). The framework is based on the inputs, which are the supply chain activities required for Supply Chain Competitiveness, and the outputs, which are the benefits resulting from that. A comprehensive review of the literature is conducted to address key issues related to supply chain competitiveness, and its determinants, and its various dimensions, followed by an exploration of Supply Chain Competitiveness. Drawing insights from the review, a conceptual framework for Supply Chain Competitiveness is presented, focusing on its activities, an environment, and the outcomes also. The conceptual framework illustrates the bi-directional flow of information at all levels, with interrelated activities within a globally competitive environment. These activities encompass the roles of suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors, with a stronger emphasis on manufacturers' activities. Furthermore, the implications of various factors such as economic, political, legal, technical, socio-cultural, competition, and demographic aspects are also highlighted. The Supply Chain Competitiveness framework aims to address the relatively understudied area of supply chain competitiveness. It is anticipated that this work will inspire further research and

engagement from scholars, researchers, and practitioners in this field, while offering conceptual guidance for enhancing its performance.

Keywords—Competitive advantage, supply chain, Supply Chain Competitiveness (SSC), supply chain management.

Introduction

The intense rivalry in the current market is driven by advancements in industrial technology, growing globalization, and significant enhancements in the accessibility of information [1]. Organizations have been compelled to undergo significant changes due to competitive priorities arising from escalating customer expectations, ever-increasing global competition, competition based on time and quality, and the demand for mass customization [2]. In the 1980s and 1990s, industrial development brought about significant changes in the market conditions for industrial activities. Terms such as networks, strategic alliances, and other forms of quasi-integration accurately depict the transformed nature of industrial activities during this period. As a result, organizations have been compelled to reconsider their operations, alliances, partnerships, and strategies in order to adapt to these and similar changes. Supply chain management (SCM) has emerged as a crucial element of competitive strategy, aiming to enhance organizational productivity, profitability, and competitive success. **Fig. 1** illustrates the components of the supply chain that contribute to achieving supply chain competitiveness.

Fig.1 Supply chain elements

Currently, there is a growing need to manage and improve Supply Chain Competitiveness (SCC) since the true competition lies between supply chains rather than individual companies [3]. The significance of supply chain competitiveness (SCC) is increasing because organizations can only survive in this globally competitive environment if they are competitive enough in terms of both supply chain performance and customer satisfaction.

This paper aims to emphasize the significance of SCC, examine SCC-related issues, and propose a conceptual framework for SCC. The objectives of the paper are threefold: (1) to comprehend the concepts of supply chain and supply chain competitiveness; (2) to emphasize the importance of supply chain competitiveness; and (3) to present a conceptual framework for SCC. The paper is structured as follows: it begins with highlight the importance of SCC, address SCC-related issues, and propose a conceptual framework for SCC. This paper aims to emphasize the significance of SCC, examine SCC-related issues, and propose a conceptual framework for SCC. The objectives of the paper are threefold: (1) to comprehend the concepts of supply chain and supply chain competitiveness; (2) to emphasize the importance of supply chain competitiveness; and (3) to present a conceptual framework for SCC. The paper is organized as follows: it begins with a literature review, followed by the presentation of a conceptual framework for SCC. Finally, concluding remarks are provided along with suggestions for future research directions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several researchers have extensively studied different aspects of supply chain and supply chain management, including definitions, dimensions, performance measurement, frameworks, applications, strategies, and related concepts. These studies have been supported by empirical research conducted in various enterprise-related domains such as supply, manufacturing, retailing, distribution and transportation, inventory management, information flows, demand management, value chains, customer satisfaction, and more. In the context of this paper, the literature can be

categorized into three main sections: supply chain, supply chain management, and supply chain competitiveness.

1. Supply Chain

The field of supply chain has been extensively studied by numerous researchers and practitioners, approaching it from various perspectives and applications. In **Table 1**, we present a collection of selected concepts and definitions related to the supply chain.

Table 1: Select concepts and definitions of supply chain

Author	Definition
[4]	The supply chain refers to the interconnected network of organizations involved in various upstream and downstream activities and processes that contribute to the creation of value in the form of products and services, ultimately delivered to the end consumer
[5]	A group of companies that transfer materials in a forward direction.
[6]	The coordination of companies involved in bringing products or services to the market, which encompasses the final customers, as an integral part of the supply chain.
[2]	A set of three or more entities (organizations or individuals) directly involved in the upstream and downstream flows of products, services, finances, and/or information from a source to a customer.

Based on the information provided in the table, a general definition of supply chain can be stated as follows: "A network comprising of organizations or individuals that are directly engaged in the upstream and downstream movements of products, services, finances, information, and value, spanning from a source to the end customers.

2Supply chain Management

Numerous researchers have dedicated their efforts to exploring the concept of supply chain management (SCM). Table II provides a compilation of significant definitions and concepts related to supply chain management.

Table 2: Select definitions and concepts of supply chain management

Author	Definition
[7]	It encompasses the comprehensive movement of materials, spanning from suppliers to end users.
[8]	The objective is to align customer requirements with the flow of materials from suppliers, aiming to achieve a balance between seemingly conflicting goals of superior customer service, efficient inventory management, and cost optimization.
[5]	When two or more firms within a supply chain establish a long-term agreement, foster trust and commitment in their relationship, integrate logistics activities by sharing demand and sales data, there is potential for a shift in the control of the logistics process.
[9]	Strategic management of the movement and storage of materials, parts, and finished goods inventory is involved in the process of ensuring an efficient flow from suppliers through the organization and ultimately to the customer.

Based on the information provided in the table, an alternative definition of supply chain management can be stated as follows: "Supply chain management is a collection of interconnected activities aimed at managing relationships with suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers, and customers. The objective is to provide exceptional customer value at reduced cost through efficient and effective distribution, purchasing, procurement, and other supply chain activities. This is achieved through a seamless flow of information, emphasizing customer service, and gaining a competitive advantage."

3Supply chain competitiveness

For a considerable period of time, researchers have been endeavoring to define and conceptualize supply chain competitiveness (SCC), exploring an extensive array of strategies in the process. As stated in reference [14], mass customization is highlighted as a means to significantly enhance variety and customization, while maintaining efficiency, effectiveness, and cost-effectiveness. The emphasis is placed on utilizing mass customization as a strategy to enhance the competitiveness of supply chains. In contrast, according to reference [15], the adoption of information and communication technologies is deemed as the most significant and influential change that impacts both companies and supply chain competitiveness. The utilization of internet and other communication systems is suggested as a means to enhance SCC. Additionally, operations strategy is recognized as a fundamental competitive tool that focuses on two key aspects: process and content, as highlighted by reference [16]. The vital role of operations management and operations strategy in achieving SCC is well-documented by references [16], [17], [18], and [13]. Furthermore, [19] argues that operational activities serve as the fundamental building blocks of competitive advantage, emphasizing that the operational effectiveness of a business directly contributes to competitiveness and market leadership.

In the current era, supply chain competitiveness has garnered significant importance due to the challenges confronted by organizations in the global business environment. Reference [20] asserts that companies can effectively compete by fostering and managing cooperative and collaborative partnerships. Moreover, according to [22], flexibility plays a pivotal role in enhancing the competitiveness of the supply chain. Additionally, [21] suggests that agility surpasses flexibility and cost efficiency as a competitive priority. Furthermore, reference [23] highlights information, intelligence, and expertise as critical organizational resources for gaining a competitive advantage.

Table 3: Supply chain competitiveness strategies

Author	SCC Strategy
[2]	Customer orientation, Demand Management
[14]	Mass customization
[15]	Information and Communication
[16]	Process capabilities
[19]	Operational effectiveness
[13]	Operations Strategy
[20]	Coordination, Cooperation, Collaboration, Flexibility

FRAMEWORK FOR SCC

The conceptual framework of SCC is divided in three parts:

- (A) SCC inputs,
- (B) SCC environment
- (C) SCC outcomes

1. SCC inputs

The inputs for supply chain competitiveness (SCC) encompass a range of activities that need to be carried out at various levels of the supply chain to attain SCC. These activities are essential for gaining competitive advantages. This section consists of the following activities:

- Flexibility refers to the ability to adapt and adjust processes, products, and services to meet the changing requirements of customers. It is a crucial factor that organizations must prioritize in order to cope with evolving customer demands and gain a competitive advantage. This aspect has been emphasized by references [20], [21], and [22].

- The four C's of supply chain competitiveness (SCC) are coordination, cooperation, collaboration, and customer orientation. These four aspects must be taken into consideration. In order for supply chains to attain competitiveness, it is crucial to

achieve coordination, cooperation, and collaboration among the various elements of the chain, as

highlighted by references [20] and [21]. Additionally, satisfying customers is imperative for gaining competitive advantages, and therefore, customer orientation is a vital factor for SCC, as emphasized by reference [2].

- The attainment of supply chain competitiveness relies on the synergy among supply chains, as stated in reference [2]. This implies that the combined results and achievements should surpass the combined inputs and resources. In other words, the overall outcomes should outweigh the collective inputs.

- Mass customization is a strategy that enables a significant expansion in product variety and customization while maintaining efficiency, effectiveness, and cost-effectiveness, as highlighted in reference [14]. By adopting mass customization, supply chains can enhance their competitiveness without compromising on these crucial factors.

- Supply chain flow cycles refer to the smooth and uninterrupted movement of materials, information, and funds within the supply chains. In order for supply chains to achieve competitiveness, it is essential that these flows are facilitated efficiently and effectively, as emphasized in references [2], [15], and [27].

- The integration of essential components such as supplier's suppliers, suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers, customers, and customer's customers is vital within the supply chain. This integration is a critical requirement to achieve supply chain competitiveness (SCC), as emphasized in reference [24].

- Demand and product management are vital activities within the supply chain for achieving supply chain competitiveness (SCC) [2, 27]. Managing demand involves meeting customer requirements, while product management focuses on optimizing product offerings. Successfully executing these activities provides competitive advantages in the market.

- Strategic alliances are cooperative partnerships pursued to gain strategic benefits [24, 27].

- Agility is the rapid adaptation to changing customer demands and is a key activity for achieving supply chain competitiveness (SCC) [20, 21, 25].

2. SCC environment

The competitive environment comprises both the business and global contexts. The business environment encompasses factors such as competitor strategies, evolving customer demands, financial considerations, market conditions, social and economic forces, government policies, and socioeconomic factors. On the other hand, the global environment includes the global scenario, behavioral forces, economic conditions, cultural influences, and foreign trade policies [31]. The competitiveness of the environment is shaped by the flow of information and funds, both in the forward and backward directions.

3. SCC outcomes

Gaining supply chain competitiveness (SCC) is accomplished through the execution of the activities outlined in part A. The outcomes associated with SCC are as follows:

- Value to the customers
- Customers' Satisfaction
- Responsiveness to quick changes
- Innovation
- Improvement in the products and services
- Profitability to the organization
- Competitive Advantage
- One of the outcomes of supply chain competitiveness (SCC) is the delivery of value to customers. SCC enables the provision of high-quality products at reduced costs, thereby offering customers enhanced value. Adding value to products is an inherent characteristic of SCC, as it focuses on improving product quality and affordability, leading to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty.

- Customer satisfaction is a crucial outcome of supply chain competitiveness (SCC). The more competitive the supply chain, the higher the level of customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction, in turn, contributes to the competitive success of the supply chain.

- SCC improves supply chain flexibility and agility, resulting in increased organizational responsiveness. This means that organizations can respond more quickly to changing situations.

- Innovation is a significant outcome of supply chain competitiveness (SCC) as it bridges the gap between customer requirements and reality. Through innovation, supply chains can achieve competitiveness by effectively managing both demand and product chains, ultimately satisfying customers' needs and preferences. Innovation plays a crucial role in aligning supply chain activities with customer expectations and driving continuous improvement within the supply chain.

- SCC leads to increased profitability, which is the ultimate goal for any organization.

- Supply chain competitiveness (SCC) leads to a competitive advantage, which, in turn, results in profitability and lower product costs. SCC enables organizations to differentiate themselves from competitors, gain market share, and achieve sustainable profitability by effectively managing their supply chains. By optimizing processes, reducing costs, and delivering value to customers, organizations can establish a competitive edge in the marketplace.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this article has introduced a comprehensive conceptual framework for Supply Chain Competitiveness (SCC), offering a structured view of the pivotal activities, the dynamic environment, and the resulting outcomes that define SCC. It is important to underscore the interconnectedness of these activities, which collectively play a vital role in enabling organizations to enhance their supply chain management and ultimately attain competitiveness. The proposed framework carries several significant advantages. Firstly, it provides a clear understanding of the distinct

activities and responsibilities of key stakeholders such as suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors in the pursuit of SCC. Secondly, it lays a solid foundation for future research endeavors within the domain of supply chain competitiveness, guiding scholars and practitioners alike in their pursuit of knowledge and innovation. Moreover, this framework is a valuable tool for organizations aiming to assess and improve their own supply chain competitiveness. By offering a structured overview of the essential components of SCC, it enables organizations to identify specific areas for enhancement and tailor their supply chain strategies accordingly. To further validate the efficacy of this framework, it is imperative to develop separate modules for suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors, ensuring that their roles and interactions are comprehensively addressed. The seamless flow of information in both directions, across various levels of the supply chain, is essential to minimize distortions and optimize supply chain management practices. Additionally, this article emphasizes the need for empirical investigations into the activities, environmental factors, and outcomes that influence supply chain competitiveness. Such research endeavors will be instrumental in quantifying the impact of these elements on actual supply chain performance, thereby adding empirical rigor to the conceptual framework. In summary, this article's insights serve as a foundational resource for academia, organizational leaders, and supply chain practitioners. By providing a robust conceptual framework for SCC, it empowers stakeholders to make informed decisions, drive improvements, and navigate the complex landscape of supply chain competitiveness with clarity and purpose. As the pursuit of SCC continues to evolve, this framework offers a steadfast guide for those seeking to thrive in an increasingly competitive global marketplace.

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